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Impact of Digitalisation and Students Examinations in Higher Institutions in Rivers State, 2012-2024

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ABSTRACT

The process of digitalising students's examinations began in Nigeria thirteen years ago, through JAMB administered Computer Based Test (CBT). Despite its challenges, the Federal Government chose to digitise all academic examinations by 2027, prompting the question, how prepared is the government, students, lecturers and higher institutions? This paper, 'Impact of Digitalisation on Students's Examinations in Higher Institutions in Rivers State, 2012-2024', examines current state of digitalisation, challenges of integrity of examinations and result gathering system in higher institutions. Theoretical underpinning was based on Diffusion of Innovation theory and Technology Acceptance Model. It adopted both primary and secondary sources of data, with simple statistical tools for analysis. The findings revealed that most public institutions lack the necessary infrastructural facilities for digitalising all examinations, compounded by poor internet connectivity and power supply. The paper concluded that digitalising examinations is laudable, but to achieve greater progress, attention must focus on adopting digital tools, before, during and after examination. Also, maintaining integrity of examinations demands the closure of loopholes that encourage sharp practices. It recommended that e-learning should be prioritised before e-examination. Sustainability of digitalisation for academic functionality, should kick-start with practical teaching/learning across all educational levels, powered by adequate digital facilities.

Keywords: Examination; Digitalisation; Digital Initiatives; Higher institutions; Innovation.

INTRODUCTION

African Union (AU) policy framework on renewed digital initiatives, and Global AI submit on Africa, supports digitalizing the educational sector. The Federal Government of Nigeria secured \$40 million ICT project to digitize tertiary education, showing national commitment to human capital development, digital transformation and inclusive education (FGN, 2025). Prior to this, in 2001, a National Information Technology policy aimed at making Nigeria a key player in Information Technology by the year 2020 was adopted. Following this, 2018 was to be the target year as the National University Commission (NUC) came up with a blueprint for revitalizing digital literacy with Open and Long Distance Learning for higher education (FGN, 2025). In alignment with the demand to use digital tools for innovative academic activities in higher institutions. The digitalisation of all examinations in the educational sector (NTA, 2025, 3rd May), is one of the objectives of Nigeria's National Digital Economy and E-governance Bill 2024.

Also, the National Digital drive of the Federal Government of Nigeria, aligns with the theme for 2021 International Literacy Day, which focused on 'Narrowing the Digital Divide'. The Framework is to achieve 95% targets of digital literacy by 2030. What is the possibility that individuals can access this digital knowledge (Amadi, and Osai, 2024), with just 5 years to attaining the targets of 95% digital literacy. How prepared are the federal and state governments, students, lecturers and higher institutions in achieving these targets? As this requires incorporating acquisition of digital skills into the curriculum, to be taught from primary schools to the highest level of academic pursuits. Over the years, Nigerian government's attention has mostly concentrated in automating administrative services, rather than academic activities. So, the burden increases on higher institutions to embrace digital transformation as a driver of both administrative and academic excellence. According to Ogbonna (2011), 78% of Nigerian universities are hoisted on web with a functional on-line presence, (with) registration of students and courses...the school portal administer, store, retrieve and manage contents on semester examination, it also transmit scores/results.

The innovative steps to digitize administration of examination began with National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) in 2001, enabled through blended learning strategy of online/face-to-face facilitation (NOUN, 2022). During the 2012/2013 academic session, Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), adopted and administered e-examination, in form of Computer-Based Test(CBT), for candidates writing Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination(UTME). Thus facilitating the yearly admission of thousands of students into various higher institutions of learning. Individual universities also adopted the CBT format for Post-UTME entry assessment into higher institutions. This processes involved administering examination digitally, making use of desktop computers and servers to assess and evaluate learner's cognitive abilities. Since 2013, this innovation enabled JAMB in conducting digitally manage entrance examination for candidates seeking admission into tertiary institutions. The Board controls digital registrations, through processes that culminates in CBT/examination, and placement of successful students in institutions of their choices. The CBT initiative impacts on the integrity of JAMB. About 75% of 1,955,069 candidates who sat for the 2025 examination did not score up to 200 mark requirements (Juwe, 2025, June, 13th), meaning they performed below expectations. JAMB recorded poor performance, reasons given were; technical hitches, disappearing questions due to malfunctioning computers, and logging out of candidates before the finishing time. In what ways has these challenges affected the quality of digital assessment and integrity of students's examination?

This year alone, JAMB delisted 113 CBT centres for sharp practices. For the first time since inception the Board conducted resit and mop-up examination for 96,838 candidates in 183 centres (Benjamin, 2025). These malpractices in CBT system has tested the integrity of how candidates are prepared and assessed for the examination. The fact that most candidates coming from public secondary schools were never taught digitally, has never been seen as an issue. In other words, e-examinations are done without any form of exposure to e-learning for some category of candidates, especially those from rural schools, that is the government never considered it a necessity. Apart from conducting examination, are there policy frameworks earmarked for digitilisation of academic aspect of learning? Rogers, (2003) in his work

revealed that "we know too much about innovation successes and not enough about innovation failures(p.11). This paper is focused on both the innovation, successes and failures, as we investigate the impact of digitalisation of examination in higher institutions.

Research Questions

The paper poses the following research questions;

1. What is the state of digitalisation of student's examination in higher institutions in Rivers State?
2. What are the challenges of digitalising students's examination in higher institutions in Rivers State?
3. What are the impact of digitalisation on the integrity of examination system?

Theoretical Underpinning

For theoretical construct, the paper adopted Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory. DOI was popularized by Everett Rogers, in 1962, with the publication of a Seminar work titled; 'Diffusion of Innovations' (Rogers, 2003). DOI theory was adopted because it operates a three dimensional approach of assessing the adoption of digital innovation, implementation, and post-adoption behaviour (Kapoor, Dwivedi, and Williams, 2014) of participants and beneficiaries of the adopted system. The relevance of DOI to this paper is its ability for incorporating technical innovations with curriculum development, in addition to administration of students examination. There is also Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989). This model is based on such factors as Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use, maintaining the usefulness and easiness of accepting new technologies. Due to its openness to innovativeness, these theories becomes useful in the area of adopting digital tools and innovative methods of e-learning, such that learners are no longer limited by distance, also for administering examinations, and assessing the outcome. Higher Institutions of learning in Rivers State can leverage on these innovations, by maximizing the usefulness of latest digital tools for teaching and administering examinations, to enhance transparency, while minimizing sharp practices (Amadi & Ewa, 2018).

Conceptual Review

Digitalisation

In the context of this study, digitalisation describes the phenomenon of adopting digital technologies for educational, societal and other purposes. For Webster Dictionary, digitalisation is the process of converting processes or something to digital form. This essentially means reworking or rewiring an existing system of doing things, to improve productivity, switching to digital tools, and smart devices, so as to achieve quicker result. Digitalisation is all about connectivity to outside world. Generally its an innovative approach which has transformed educational activities. "To digitise education does not mean to ignore traditional teaching and learning activities, rather, digitisation is the catalyst that facilitates the digitalisation of education by bridging the traditional to the ever widening virtual classroom --Getrude Shotte. The digital era is characterized by a scenario where technology, machines, and humans are connected and interacting in real-time, making it difficult to distinguish who is performing the service (Castells, 2000). This involves affiliated changes in the connectivity of individuals, organizations, and objects (Urbach and Röglinger, 2019).

Digitalisation enhances easy and quick tracking (of information) and reduction in documentation errors (Iheanacho and Oluwafemi, 2022). This is talking about much faster and easier way of verification of documents, enabling the creation of some level of accountability. In the digital era, globalisation and the rapid evolution of digital technologies are bringing diverse and complex changes to society (Schwab, 2016). The new educational curriculum introduced by Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council have incorporated Basic digital literacy from primary 4, to JSS level, with digital technologies adopted as one of the five core compulsory subjects for senior secondary students. The relevance of digitalisation of learning and examination is that students use these tools to access various learning topics, prepare adequately for computer based examinations.

Higher Institutions

Higher institutions are citadel of academic, administrative, technical and commercial activities, with numerous opportunities. Its objectives in Nigeria is to provide trainings, enhancing people's intellectual and physical abilities (National Policy on Education(2013). Pursued through teaching, research development, and generation of dissemination of knowledge (Amadi, 2024). Incorporating new technologies for educational sector is now in vogue, as it is enabling free flow of information. Higher institutions includes; Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Technology, Education, and Health Sciences. Higher educational sector are under increasing pressure to use the new Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to instruct their students with the knowledge and skills they need in this 21st century (UNESCO, 2012). Since learning has extended beyond conventional instructions in classrooms, with traditional paper work. Demands on educational institutions to innovate, and adopt digital tools for teaching skills and the knowledge that students needs, in order to participate meaningfully in innovative and creative activities is on the rise globally. Besides, every student or learner is tested through one examination or the other for their certification.

Examinations

What is examination and how is it administered? Examination is designed to test, assess and evaluate the lessons and the learning outcome of classroom interactions. Administration of examination is an all-inclusive process, starting with lectures, teaching/learning, setting questions, administering examination, invigilation, marking of answer scripts, compilation, computation of scores, submission of results and approval, then the onward transmission to ICTCs, where students' results are digitally managed for uploading. Examination agents includes, the examiners, students, invigilators and school authorities, who liaise to avoid sharp practices during the process.

For digitally administered examination system, the questions and instructions are transmitted and shared electronically. UTME conducted by JAMB, and Post-UTME conducted by various universities. NOUN is also involved in digitalisation and innovation. Adopting blended learning strategy for its Open Distance Learning (ODL) programmes, and has graduated a total of 134,010 students between 2009 and 2022 (NOUN, 2022). In this case, officially e-learning precede e-examination, Instructors use both face-to-face and online facilitation platforms, deploying techniques like teleconferences, audio, Open Educational Resources (OER), with Massive Open Online Courses (NOUN, 2022, p.39). The adoption of digital tools by higher institutions for e-examination enhances the flexibility of accessing examination papers, previous year question papers anytime, anywhere, and also have easy access to resource persons, mentors, experts, researchers, professionals, and peers all over the world (Noor-UI-Amin, 2012).

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopted a mixed research method, using both survey, and quantitative data, as well as descriptive techniques. Nature and sources of data was basically triangulation, both primary and secondary data was used. 3030 registered NOUN undergraduate and postgraduate students made up the population of the study. Taro Yarmane formula was used to calculate the sample size of 353 students, who responded to the 'Impact of Digitalization on Students an Examinations in Higher Institutions in Rivers State' (IDSEHIRS) Questionnaire. Out of the 353, 345 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved. In addition to data from in-dept interview from 10 Lecturers purposively selected. It sought secondary data from academic journals, and other published works. Qualitative descriptive method and simple statistical tools of frequency and percentages were used for data analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Question 1: *What is the state of digitalisation of student’s examination in higher institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Response to the state of digitalisation of students examination in higher institutions

Item/Statement	Yes/ Response	No /%	Total / % N = 345
1. Is your school equipped with desktop computers and other digital accessories?	165 (48%)	180 (52%)	345 (100%)
2. Do you prefer academic activities that is automated in your school?	300 (87%)	45 (13%)	345 (100%)
3. Is your semester examinations automated?	279 (81%)	66 (19% }	345 (100%)
4. Does your school operate e-learning	238 (69%)	107 (31%)	345 (100%)
5. Does your school operates a mixture of traditional Pen-on-Paper and e-administration.	204 (89%)	141 (11%)	345 (100%)
6. Are you versatile in the usage of digital tools for academic and examination purposes.	203 (60%)	142 (40%)	345 (100%)
7. Do you agree with the planned policy of digitalizing all examinations ?	189 (55%)	156 (45%)	345 (100%)
8. Are results speedily assessed when it comes to digital examination?	296 (86%)	49 (14%)	345 (100%)

Source: Field Work, 2025

Item 1 in Table 1, 165 or 48% affirms that their school is equipped with digital accessories, while 180 or 52% answered in the negative. Item 3 in Table 1, 279 or 81% of the response to semester examination is automated, said yes, while 66 or 19 % said no. Item 4, 238 or 69% of the respondents accepted that their school operate e-learning, while 107 or 31% replied in the negative. Item 5, 204 or 89% says yes to the question of school operating a mixture of pen-on-paper and e-administration, while 141 or 11% said no. Presently publicly owned higher institutions transverse between traditional administrative method and digitally managed processes. On admission students do e-payment of fees and e-registration of courses, which enables access to school portal, and participation in semester examination. After marking, results are transmitted online for accessibility. Generally, there is a mixture of e-learning and Pen-on-Paper method of administering examinations at NOUN, and in some Private universities. In public institutions, the PoP style is adopted for teaching and learning and for the conduct of examinations. Whereas the answer scripts are marked and results compiled manually, and transmitted through ICT servers. Uploading of students result is digitally managed, they access it from their Portal, in some cases they are pasted on the notice board. Excerpt from in-dept interview, on how policy of digitalisation of examination in higher institutions in Rivers State have been implemented? SV1. *It is assumed that students going in for a digitally administered examination have been practically taught and are versatile with digital tools, whereas that is not the reality. The issue of automating examination, before automating academic tasks is challenging. A whole lot is not adding up. A policy that did not make provision for students to learn digitally, yet forces them to write examination digitally, is not reasonable.*

Question 2: *What are the challenges of digitalising students's examination in higher institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2 : Response to the challenges of digitalising students's examination in higher institutions.

Items/Statements	Yes / %	No /%	Total /%
1. Naiveness and unpreparedness make students to grapple and participate in some sharp practices during examination.	250 (60%)	95 (40%)	345(100%)
2. Intermittent electricity supply and Internet network services, give undue advantage to some candidates against others. This is a big challenge to digitalised examination.	223(70%)	122(30%)	345(100%)
3. Inequalities in accessing digital tools leads to poor grade in e-examination.	201 (58%)	144(42%)	345(100%)
4. Digital literacy is more theoretical than practical, as students are taught on PoP in most public schools and at all educational levels.	298 (86%)	47 (14%)	345(100%)
5. Some students use the digital tools to undermine the integrity of examination	83 (24%)	262(76%)	345(100%)
6. High Cost of Laptops and data subscription is a limitation to digital transformation for some students	157 (46%)	88 (54%)	345(100%)

Source: Field Work, 2025.

In Table 2, Item 1, 250 or 60% of respondents says yes to the statement that some category of students are naive, and unprepared digitally to face the computer-based examinations, while 95 or 40% replied in the negative. In Item 2, 223 or 70% of respondents agree with the assertion that infrastructural deficit around the country is a limiting factor, while 122 or 30% says no.

The fact that facilities for administering examinations digitally is insufficient, and at worst virtually non-existent in most public schools, is a limitation to digitalisation. Apart from technical/system failures, students are taught with the traditional method of pen-on-paper, and chalkboard, then they are required to write examination digitally, with UTME recording more failures each year. The make-up or mop-up examination and spill overs, shows that the system is still facing some technical hitches and human related challenges. Lawan, and Mohammed (2020), reveals that unstable electricity supply, ICT illiteracy and poor network infrastructure are challenges of e-service delivery in Nigeria. On the other hand, after studying impact of e-governance in two tertiary institutions in Kaduna state Ikechukwu,(2022) attest that e-governance has improved service delivery in JAMB, although inadequate infrastructure like electricity is a major impediment to JAMB. The issue of inequality in accessing digital tools and Internet services, is a real concern. Inequalities exist between urban-based schools and schools in rural areas, between public schools and privately run ones (Wordu, 2020).

Question 3: *How has digitalisation of examinations impacted the integrity of examinations and result gathering system?*

Table 3: Response on how digitalisation of examination has impacted on integrity of examinations and result gathering system.

Item/Statement	Yes / %	No / %	Total %
1. Has e-examination made you to be more confident when writing examination?	286 (56%)	69 (44%)	345(100%)
2. Do you entertain any fear that the digital servers for examination can be hacked ?	94 (79%)	251 (80%)	345(100%)
3. Do you prepare for your examination now than you did before?	269 (78%)	76 (22%)	345(100%)
4. Would you want to continue your postgraduate programmes, after you graduate in this NOUN?	302 (89%)	43 (11%)	345(100%)
5. Do you experience delays in getting your results?	25 (7%)	320 (93%)	345(100%)

6. Are you more versatile now in the usage of digital tools for examination and other purposes?	288 (83%)	57 (27%)	345(100%)
7. Do you agree with the policy of digitalising all examinations?	313 (91%)	32 (9%)	345(100%)
8. Has digitalisation of examination reduced cases of impersonation?	269 (78%)	76 (22%)	345(100%)

Source : Field Work, 2025.

In Table 3, Item 3, 269 or 78% of respondents agrees that the system has made students to adequately prepare for each examination, knowing that their success or failure is in their hands. While 76 or 22% do not think so. For Item 4, 302 or 89% of the respondents would want to go back to pursue their postgraduate programmes, and 43 or 11% says no. Also, for Item 8, 269 or 78% of the respondents says yes that digitalisation has drastically reduced cases of impersonation during examination, while 76 or 22%. The paper shows that there is high level of acceptance amongst students and their lecturers who are the end users, hence depicting NOUN as a success story. Usage of digital tools for administering and participating in examinations has created some positive impacts amongst students, though not in all cases. The fact is that any academic environment that is digitised increases students' independence. That is to say, "digital education puts the responsibility and the power into the hands of the learner"--George Veletsionos. It also helps in improving instructor professional development, offering schools the opportunity for global visibility. Meanwhile World Bank (2022) reiterated the fact that e-learning platforms "reduce paper work, and support monitoring of teacher and students performance", during examination. Digitalisation has in-built system to enable students manage the time allotted, while processing the correct answers. The outcome is speedy assessments of results. Since machines does the marking with the scoring and instantaneously results are displayed once the students submit and log out. It has also drastically minimised inefficiency in the handling of students results and reducing cases of impersonation. Its cost-effectiveness cannot be compared. On the other hand, the human challenges are issues of persons compromising examination with some candidates using Smartphones, Smartpen, Smartwatch, etcetera.

Which do you prefer, manual, digital or a mixture of both systems? He replied; SV2: *"I have gone digital with my postgraduate classes, sometimes we use zoom meeting or WhatsApp Voice or Video Chats for our lectures, but not during examination. This is a personal arrangement and not an institutional policy".* SV3: *For now, a mixed method will be better, because that e-examination has been tested in other climes and it is working for them, there is no guarantee that it will work for us, beside we do not have the technology like China where they regulate, monitor or manage the other side of digitalisation. If you want to build or rebuild a structure, you start from the foundation, prepare the ground first before you lay your blocks.*

In the same digitally administered examination, some candidates have access to Internet services, while others do not. The question is how e-services can be made available and accessible to majority of the students, since inaccessibility could create gaps in transition to digitalising examination process. This may require institutions making arrangement with network providers for accessibility and uninterrupted services in various campuses. Tide Newspaper has it that the Rivers State University has began the journey of transitioning to full digitalisation, working in partnership with Globacom, a network provider, to install seven network masks, to improve digital learning and durable efficient network services, cutting across four Campuses in Rivers State University(Tide, 2025). Lecturers have also received free glo SIM cards, based on this arrangement. On the question 'What is the solution to the challenges of intermittent power outages? SV4: *"I will suggest that they migrate to alternative sources of energy, depending on their location, engineering department can be empowered to harness solar, wind, and hydro energy to achieve uninterrupted power supply in our campuses".*

Recently, the Sequential Actor Result Presentation (SARP) model was adopted by the Rivers State University. It identified four cardinal focal areas in most examinations, they are; I. Examination administration; ii. Result compilation and presentation; iii. Computation of Results and; iv. Digital Result Management. "the process sets a defined timeline from lecturers submitting results two weeks after examination, to students assessing Senate-approved results online by eighth week. Explaining the commitment to a system where examination results are not only accurate and timely but also reflective of fairness and academic vigour (Wele, 2025). Emphasis here is on e-examination, we are yet to see priority been given to e-learning in public schools. An assessment of digitalisation in high-brow private schools, shows that even at foundational levels, laptops are core requirement for admission for new students in primary, secondary and higher institutions. Transiting from e-learning to e-examination, is part of a new digital revolution, from the teaching, to learning, then administering semester or termly examinations. This is the proper way of introducing digitalisation, encompassing an innovative integrated approach, inclusive of teaching and assessing learning outcome digitally, e-learning comes first, before conducting e-examination.

CONCLUSION

The paper examined the process of administering examinations digitally in higher institutions in Rivers State. It found that digitising academic processes has been ignored outrightly, though, some institutions are partially embracing administrative aspect of digitalisation. The process of migrating from e-administration to e-learning have been slow in others. E-learning aspect which would have enabled improvement in the performance of students exposed to digitally administered examinations lags behind in most publicly run educational institutions in Rivers State. Rather than exploring new windows for administering examination with digital tools, some higher institutions are concerned with e-administrative processes. Amongst NOUN students, there is greater progress in adapting and harnessing digital tools, before, during and after examinations. The findings suggest that higher institutions lack necessary infrastructural facilities that enhances full digitalisation of all examinations, compounded by disruptive and poor internet connectivity. The paper concluded that the policy to fully digitise all examinations is laudable, but the process must not only concentrate on examination, but must go beyond examination itself and carter for the period before, during and after examinations. Also, without appropriate infrastructural facilities, the issue of transitioning to a digitalised academic environment will be delayed due to technical hitches, and unequal access to facilities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The paper recommends that if sustainability of digitalisation for academic functionality is to be achieved, then e-learning should be prioritised before administering e-examination or Computer-Based Test,
2. The policy of transitioning to digitalisation should kick-start with practical teaching/learning across all levels, from primary school, secondary and finally, higher institutions, powered by adequate digital facilities.
3. Basic digital tools should be provided at all educational stages, in urban and rural areas in order to reduce the digital gaps.
4. Government should provide infrastructural facilities, replace malfunctioning computer servers for hitch-free CBT examinations.
5. Examiners should get smarter, up-skill, and develop positive attitude towards the usage of digital accessories for teaching/learning, and for e-examination.
6. To achieve uninterrupted power supply, higher institutions should migrate and harness solar and wind powered source of energy, collaborate with network providers, for access to regular Internet connectivity.

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